

Framing barriers for distribution grid digitalisation: A conceptual framework for policy recommendation

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Abstract—The energy transition process has a significant impact on the energy distribution grid through an increasing decentralisation and electrification of energy resources. Digitalisation offers opportunities to support security and quality of supply in the transition process. Distribution System Operators (DSOs) need to embrace the opportunities and change their operating paradigm by leveraging on the digital solutions. This study aims to shed light on the barriers for the DSOs digitalisation process. We develop a conceptual framework that systematically links perceived or observed barriers to digital technologies and DSOs core functionalities. We identify six DSOs core functionalities that need to be improved by means of digital investments and map key implementation barriers building on a comprehensive and multi-disciplinary literature review. This cross-featuring sheds new light on the nature of best practices that can alleviate digitalisation barriers associated with various DSOs functionalities.

Index Terms-- Digitalisation, Distribution System Operator, Barrier analysis, Energy Policy, Energy Transition.

I. INTRODUCTION

The expected massive growth of variable energy sources in electricity generation coupled with a multiplication of electricity uses requires a profound rethink of the way electricity is used and transported via the grid. To express the magnitude of this ongoing transformation, [1] and [2] describe a paradigm shift, especially affecting decentralised users and the distribution grid. The major transformations can be broken down into three main pillars at the end-user level [3] (i) the acceleration of the electrification of end uses, (ii) the increase of decentralised production, for the most part also variable, and (iii) the activation of flexibility resources, themselves dependent on the first two pillars. This backdrop of technical change at the end-users' part in turn raises the question of management of the distribution grids. Distribution grid operators (DSOs) now face new responsibilities which increasingly require greater operational flexibility, for which a shift to more digital solutions seems inevitable, as advocated by [4], [5].

By digitalisation, we mean application of digital solutions in a given sector [6]. Applied to energy distribution grid, digital

technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, the internet of things (IoT) or blockchain, can provide new ways of optimizing grid operation and at the same time supporting the energy transition.

However, a general observation is that in the last ten years we have seen a boom in installation of smart meters, but the "digitalisation" of distribution networks has remained very limited[7]. Also, we observe a growing gap between public policy foresight regarding utilities digitalisation, numerous research on the topic and then the realities on the ground.

This research work aims at shedding new light on the why and where questions: Why does this gap exist? What prevents a widespread adoption of digital technologies on the low voltage grid? And where does this "digital gap" take place? What activities could the DSOs implement, and which benefits could they gain from digital adoption but remain in fact untouched?

We use an original approach building on an extended literature review to build a conceptual framework serving the systematic analysis of this digital gap. In doing so, we categorize and frame current DSOs' core functionalities, associate key technologies enhancing them, and connect them to a set of barriers affecting the adoption process. Ultimately, we create new knowledge on the dynamics affecting the DSOs' digitalisation process with the aim of formulating policy recommendations.

The remainder of this work is as follows: Section II defines the key elements of the proposed framework by introducing the DSOs Core Functionalities, a catalogue of digital technologies and a classification of barriers. Section III shows the logic of the developed framework and the method used for its implementation. Section IV analyses the results of the analysis carried out while Section V concludes with a set of final remarks, limitations and future perspectives.

II. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The study is based on a three-stage approach. First, we build on desk studies to qualify our understanding of DSOs' digitalisation. We identify six main core functionalities, ten main classes of digital technologies and five barrier types. We then developed our framework of analysis focusing on the relationship between functionalities, technologies, and barriers. Finally, a systematic search of scientific articles was

carried out to investigate this link and shed light on the difficulties encountered by DSOs in applying innovative digital solutions to support their core functionalities.

A. Step 1: Qualifying DSO's digitalisation

1) DSOs core functionalities going digital

Past research discusses several functionalities operated by DSOs and proposes a perspective of their evolution according to their digitalisation [3],[8]–[11]. Among these functionalities, some were very specific to a particular use case (e.g. specific to a local grid operation) which prevents a generalizable analysis and was consequently left aside to focus on the core functionalities. Building on this corpus, we identify six core functionalities and related sub-functionalities, shown in Table I.

TABLE I. DSOS CORE FUNCTIONALITIES AND SUB-FUNCTIONALITIES

Core Functionalities	Sub-Functionalities	Ref.
System Operations	1)Monitoring and control; 2) Balancing and demand; 3) Responding to disturbance and outage;	[3], [8]
System Management	1)Network communication and coordination 2) Regulatory compliance. 3)Customer relationship management;	[10], [12]
Network Planning	1)Load forecasting; 2) System analysis; 3) Network optimization; 4) Integration of DER;	[11], [13]
Asset Management	1)Asset identification; 2) Asset condition assessment; 3) Asset data management; 4) Asset Performance monitoring; 5) Asset maintenance; 6) Asset performance optimization; 7) Asset cost management; 8) Asset risk management;	[14], [15]
Flexibility Management	1)Demand response management. 2)Volt-VAR management; 3) Ancillary services management; 4) Capacity management; 5) Market management	[9], [16], [17]
Commercial Operations	1)Billing and customer management. 2)Data Management; 3) Revenue Management; 4) Market operations; 5) Contract management; 6) Compliance management	[18], [19]

2) Catalogue of digital technologies

The portfolio of available digital technologies in the energy sector is very large and varied, encompassing a wide range of areas of applications [20].

Based on the various studies carried out on the determination of digital technologies in the energy sector [20]–[22] and considering the definitions proposed in [23]we have defined the following digital technologies catalogue. **Artificial Intelligence**: algorithms and models that can learn from data and make predictions or decisions. **Big data**: large and complex data sets which cannot be processed by traditional data processing. **Blockchain**: decentralized digital ledger allowing for secure and transparent transactions without a third party. **Internet of things**: fusion of digital and physical infrastructures, mainly trough internet-connected devices. **Cybersecurity technologies and frameworks**: tools, processes and guidelines used to protect digital systems and data from unauthorized access, theft, or damage.

Communication Infrastructure and architectures: cloud-based computing and storage solutions to manage and analyze data. **Augmented reality**: augmented real or entirely virtual worlds allowing human interaction simulated through computers. **Virtualization**: it consists either of extracting software from the hardware and deploying it on a local third-party infrastructure, or of setting up other future algorithms on the same infrastructure, all offering at least the same performance. **Digital twin**: virtual representation of physical objects in operation enabling real time simulations. **Robotics**: use of robots for design, construction and operation process.

3) Barriers identification

Multiple challenges and risk associated with digital technologies adoption are discussed in several studies [21], [24], [25].

However, to our knowledge no thorough review has attempted to provide a categorization of barriers affecting digital technology adoption by DSOs. We define five main barrier types:

- **Technical barriers**: refer to challenges that arise due to limitations or inadequacies in hardware, software, or communication technologies that prevent the successful implementation of digital solutions. In particular reference is made to legacy infrastructure [5], [26] which is not conducive to the integration of new digital technologies [22] and also leads to challenges with respect to scalability and replicability of digital solutions [27]. Furthermore, data management issues concerning the availability, governance and sharing [28], [29] also fall into this category, as well as cybersecurity and privacy risks [5], [24]. Also, to be considered are the performance of digital tools which lead to a considerable increase in energy consumption that cannot be overlooked [21], [30].
- **Organizational barriers**: refer to challenges that arise due to the structure, culture, and processes of an organization that impede the successful implementation of digital solutions. Factors such as a lack of a clear digital strategy [26], [28], cultural resistance to digital transformation [31], and the need for change management [21], [24] are considered.
- **Regulatory barriers**: refer to policies or regulations that may limit the type or scale of investments that can be made in digital technologies. Of major interest are the regulations on incentives for investment support, especially in regulated markets where total investment in physical assets is the basis of revenues, while investments in digital technologies re not incentivised [34]. Moreover, the current design of regulations produces secondary. effects that lead to inefficient behavior of the agent under regulation (e.g. time-delays in the cost recognition deter investment decisions and lead to welfare losses due to inefficient investment patterns [35]). Other barriers of this category are related to the lack of adoption of open data standards limiting interoperability and integration of digital solutions [22], [36].

Figure 1. Conceptual framework linking DSOs core functionalities, digital technologies and barriers.

- **Economic barriers:** Economic barriers include factors such as high costs, uncertain return on investment, and limited funding or resources [24], [32].
- **Human factors barriers:** refer to the various obstacles that arise from the attitudes, behaviors, and perceptions of individuals within an organization or society that can impede the successful adoption and implementation of digital technologies. These barriers can take many forms, such as resistance to change [31], lack of digital skills [21], [22], fear of job loss or reluctance to adopt new ways of working [33], as well as acceptance uncertainty from users and consumers [34].

B. Step 2: conceptual framework

This part develops the conceptual framework linking barrier types to digital technologies and the achievement of enhanced functionalities at the DSO level, as illustrated in Fig.1. We argue that different functionalities may be associated with different operating contexts, which can result in the emergence of distinct digital technologies adoption barriers. Analysing these differences is useful to support the decision-making process of DSOs by helping them to make more informed decisions and thus reduce errors and implementation time.

Hence, the logic of the framework is to start with DSOs functionalities, and for each of them to observe which digital technologies can be used for their improvement. By studying this first relationship, it is possible to highlight immediately which are the main implementable technologies and on which it is necessary to focus our attention to support a faster digitalisation process. Subsequently, the framework focuses on the link between technologies and barriers to their implementation. The nesting of technologies by single functions and then the barriers of the various technologies allow us to identify which functions are more difficult to optimise and with which barriers one must deal if DSOs decide to initiate a process of improvement of a particular function by means of digital technologies. From the study of these nested relationships, it is then possible to extrapolate a set of policy recommendations that support DSOs in the digitalisation process. The study of the relationships between technologies and functionalities is carried out through a systematic literature review that is discussed in the following section. The individual digital technology and the context of application are analyzed, and the related implementation hurdles are highlighted.

C. Step3: Systematic review

We developed a search code targeted toward locating the link between DSOs' functionalities, digital tools and barriers. The focus is on open-access research papers published in Scopus and the IEEE explore database. We obtained 219 articles as a result of the search performed and the merging of the 2 databases. Finally, 93 articles were defined as relevant to our research after the screening of abstract, title and conclusion. Details on the search criteria and the code are publicly available in a dedicated GitHub repository [35].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We identified the technologies which are currently discussed the most in the revised literature and which functionalities are given the most attention. Figure 2 shows which technologies research tends to focus its interest and it shows that AI, Big Data and IoT have the most focus. Figure 3 shows which functionalities have been taken into consideration to a greater extent and points at system operation and flexibility management as the main focuses. It is worth noting that AI and big data technologies together make up about half of the papers analysed. In terms of functionality, digitalisation for operating systems, with likewise interest in flexibility, asset and network management have focus in more than 60% of the published articles. Although commercial operations are in the interest of DSOs, still little interest is placed in its optimisation through the use of innovative digital technologies. This is likely because DSOs operate with limited digitalisation budgets and investments are targeted at the most critical processes, as in the case of operations management. Following the logic of our

Figure 2. Share of discussed digital technologies in the analysed literature.

Figure 3. Share of papers tackling specific core functionalities

framework, another interesting piece of information can be found analysing how digital technologies are used in the various functions and in particular what are the research trends. Table 2 shows this link where the current research directions are defined and where they are given more attention in accordance with the analysed literature. This first general overview sheds light on the meaning of digitalisation and concretely shows the type of technologies DSOs may have to deal with, categorised by the individual functionalities. The development of AI is by far the most analysed technology and plays an important role in the development of all digital technologies as well as Big Data and IoT. It is no coincidence that these three technologies shows almost the same trends as it must be considered that their use is interconnected and therefore the development of AI implies the development of a denser network of IoT and a developed capacity to handle large amounts of data. Following this, considerable attention is also being paid to the development of data management and processing infrastructures that mainly concern the creation of cloud environments or network configurations based on edge computing. In addition, an important share of analysis is also reserved for the development of technologies to ensure cybersecurity. It must be said, however, that most of the studies reviewed are still at the conceptual and simulation-based stage. In fact, just few implementation case studies exist. These initial considerations pave the way and show us the priorities on which we need to focus our attention in exploring the barriers. However, while the literature provides more or less detailed information about technologies and their operational context, the same cannot be said when it comes to investigating barriers. As a matter of fact, about one third of the analysed studies do not provide any details about possible implementation barriers of the proposed technologies. Figure 4 shows which barriers DSOs may encounter in the implementation of digital technologies in the various functionalities. In particular, it can be observed that technical barriers to the development of digital technologies are predominant. This trend is mainly because most of the studies analysed deal with the development of AI, and on this topic they confine themselves to providing information more on technical barriers than on other limitations. In addition, more than half of the references analysed set out problems solely relating to technical aspects (e.g. scalability, insufficient data available for model training, etc.) and make no mention of possible other barriers, which makes it difficult to provide an accurate overview of how they are effectively distributed.

TABLE II. PRIORITISATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN DSOS CORE FUNCTIONALITIES

	SO	SM	NP	AM	FM	CO
AI	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+
Virtualization	-	+	-	-	-	--
IoT	++	++	++	++	++	++
Augmented reality	-	--	--	-	--	--
Big data	++	++	++	+++	++	++
Robotics	-	--	--	-	--	---
Blockchain	+	+	-	-	+	+++
Digital twin	-	-	-	-	-	---
Cyb. Security	+	++	+	+	-	++
Communication Infrastructure	+	+	-	+	+	++

Priority scale: +++ high; ++ moderate; + limited; - minor; -- negligible; --- irrelevant

Figure 4. Implementation barriers within DSOs core functionalities

This clearly gives rise to the need for further investigation in terms of barrier analysis to provide a more realistic view of the real existing problems that hinder and slows the digitalisation process down.

However, it is possible to observe how the approach used systematically highlights the main barriers to be addressed if one intends to improve the various functionalities by means of digital technologies.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study represents a first attempt to systematically investigate the barriers hindering the widespread adoption of digital technologies for DSOs. Our approach is holistic as it consists of building a strong understanding of the digitalisation purposes and identifying obstacles associated with it. Having the core functionalities that DSOs need to fulfil as a reference in the current energy transition context, we analyse the main digital technologies and then explore the existing barriers that slow down their implementation. Through this approach, DSOs can get a clear view of the possibilities of developing their functionalities by means of digital technologies and observe the related limitations.

At this stage the work does not allow to develop a concrete strategy to remove the barriers. Rather the work provides guidelines on where and how to identify the barriers and

anticipate their impacts in terms of potentially “missed” technology and future application. This can in turn serve to layout adaptation strategies for the DSOs or regulatory agencies. The simplified showcase provides an example of how the conceptual framework can bring useful knowledge and support decision-making processes. This can help to gain a clear view of what critical functions DSOs must fulfil first, with which digital technologies it is possible to do so, and what barriers need to be overcome. However, our preliminary analysis shows some limitations. In particular, the available data are insufficient to make a true categorisation of the barriers for the development of the various functions of DSOs. Furthermore, few articles were found in relation to certain technologies such as digital twin, robotics and augmented reality. It is therefore necessary to further refine the research code with the aim of integrating more digital technologies and, above all, to acquire deeper understanding of the link between technologies and barriers. To overcome these limitations, a series of semi-structured interviews with experts from DSOs are planned and will be integrated into this analysis in the future in order to gain a clearer and more comprehensive view of the barriers to digitalisation and ultimately provide a set of robust policy recommendations and best practices.

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